

Charlottesville Holds Solutions to Global Energy Crisis

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The 2022 UN Climate Report has been released, and it translates last year's climate catastrophes into words, stating “Last year really was as bad as it seemed” ([Borenstein, Daily Progress](#)). Since then, US President Biden passed [The Willow Project](#), an Alaskan crude oil system known for its environmentally destructive and inefficient development tactics, yet another devastating attack on our ecosystem. However, locally, Charlottesville, Virginia has made leaps and bounds in its efforts toward the sustainable future of clean energy.

Local companies like Hexagon Energy, SunTribe Solar, and Apex Clean Energy all contribute renewable energy to the community's power grid. Even Ørsted, a Danish oil company turned sustainable, contributes to local Virginian projects like the Coastal Virginia Offshore Wind project (CVOW). Additionally, they work on an international level to supply the growing demand for more sustainable energies.

Concurrently, organizations like Charlottesville Climate Collaborative and Generation180 work to promote activism and awareness in our communities. Even local schools like UVA devote personnel to reassessing the sustainability of their hundreds of buildings, while JMU houses the Center for Advancement of Sustainable Energy (CASE), which is dedicated to research and establishment of clean energy and affects both national and local practices.

As a student in the Environmental Studies Academy at Western Albemarle High School, I have had the opportunity to conceptualize and complete my Senior Capstone Project by researching and advocating for the clean energy possibilities in Charlottesville.

When I began this project, I sent out ten emails to people involved in the Virginia Energy Workforce Consortium. By the time I finished, I'd spoken to 21 people specialized in their respective sustainable fields.

Initially, I was referred to Hexagon Energy, a locally based solar company dedicated to shepherding national projects through any legal restrictions of their respective communities. After projects are approved by committees at the local level, Hexagon hands off the project to a contractor, whose job it is to construct their fully fleshed-out plan.

It's important to keep in mind that any plots of land taken on by Hexagon or any solar companies must meet the regulations of the city or county they are located in, as well as any federal laws that might apply. Some restrictions include but are not limited to 50 to 100-foot buffers off of water systems, roads, paths, municipal structures, and transmission lines. Not only must there be buffers, but the terrain necessary for solar panels to be constructed must be flat. In addition, there

must be a direct line of sight to the sun for maximum efficiency, and the panels need to be kept out of the public's line of sight. They also have to be close to a substation, which is where the energy is directed before being added to the grid. Additionally, the substation must have enough storage to transfer those additional gigawatts of energy. Therefore, it is a feat to see Woodridge, Hexagon's first local project in Albemarle County, pass through the final gauntlet, and onto the construction phase.

Next I was connected to Apex Energy where I spoke with a Solar Design Associate, who works with GIS maps to assess whether solar would be effective on proposed projects, and then creates energy estimates to show that efficiency. One of their Project Manager/Developers works with landowners to convince them to lease or permit the land to Apex for their Solar or Wind arrays. Their Land Development Administrator processes the landowners' leases and permits and keeps all documents in order throughout the project. Next Energy Design Associates analyze optimal places for wind and solar farms with GIS, and reports that information to propose projects. Lastly, someone has to be in charge of finance and keep money on track for projects. These jobs represent just a small portion of careers in renewable energy.

SunTribe Solar provides the largest amount of solar power for schools in Virginia. In order to do this they use Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) with public institutions, to construct industrial-scale solar farms. PPAs allow these places to pay for the installed solar panels through the extra unused power, called renewable credits, that they produce and contribute to the grid. Much like carbon offsets, renewable credits work by allowing corporations to buy clean energy from companies that produce it, in order to offset their own emissions. This allows companies like Amazon to claim that 50% of their energy is clean, while the energy they actually use is from a coal plant down the road.

UVA's Office of Sustainability helps the university to meet its environmental goal of being carbon-neutral by 2030. They do this by reassessing the efficiency and necessity of all the buildings on campus as well as advising on new technologies to add to buildings under construction. They also provide programs and education to young people through schools in the community. Similarly, at JMU the CASE program promotes education and training in clean energy to undergrads looking for possible careers in green energy.

Next I spoke to the Senior Associate of Project Development for Ørsted Clean Energy who was able to speak to Ørsted's sustainability, such that it has been awarded the most sustainable company in the world for several years. Moreover, their global graduate program helps those interested in renewable energy rotate through some of the many fields which exist in renewable energies. One job includes reviewing plan packages and giving useful input on specific case-by-case instances.

At Charlottesville Climate Collaborative (C3) the objective is to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. C3 primarily works to help people who want to be involved in climate action but don't know how, which includes helping companies set GHG emission goals, growing the movement to make climate action a reality, and connecting people to share ideas.

Generation180 is not so different from C3 but does more work with school students in K-12 to educate our youth about environmental activism, and the importance of protecting our resources. They also run programs like Electrify Your Ride which educates people about local clean transportation options.

Commuting to and from jobs is one of the most common uses of transportation, and those jobs are being positively affected as well. Walton Shepard says, "Clean energy is the biggest job creator in our country's energy sector, employing almost three times as many workers as the fossil fuel industry." ([Yelda, Natural Resources Defense Council](#)).

It seems just about anyone can enter the green energy field, as most of the people I interviewed had all majored in different things, so the opportunities are available regardless of what choices you make in university. Virginia is looking for workers who will contribute to their own future by following the exciting, rapidly expanding field of clean energy. As Lee at Apex points out: "If you're bored in this industry, it's your own fault".

As a community, we must work to create a place where our future will be secure thanks to renewable energy. Charlottesville will serve as a precedent for small and large cities nationwide. We have a choice: to invest our valuable time and effort into a future in which the UN can state that renewable energy generation has doubled in the past decade, or one in which they state "Last year really was as bad as it seemed".

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